

Use of Game Technologies in Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language

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Abstract: This article presents thoughts and opinions about teaching Russian as a foreign language, as well as the use of various educational game methods in this process, and also talks about the culture of speech and communication, the negative effects on the state of speech culture, violation of literary norms. Formation of the culture of communication is a very complex and time-consuming process. Speech is no less important element of the system of cultural development. In the modern world it plays the role of the core of human activity. Attention is paid to increasing the vocabulary of students in foreign-language groups.

Keywords: Modern education, speech culture, speech environment, speech development, foreign language, Russian language, method, games, institution, student, grammar.

At all times the Russian language has been under the influence of other languages, which enriched it. But there are circumstances that negatively affect the state of speech culture. Violation of literary norms of pronunciation, word usage, sentence construction, impoverishment of means of linguistic expressiveness, use of parasitic words, uncommon vocabulary (jargonisms, slangs) leads to “clogging” of the speech environment.

Education has always been and remains an inexhaustible source of true knowledge and age-old wisdom, access to which gives a person the freedom and realization of his talents and the opportunity to succeed.

The development of education as the most important sphere of human activity that ensures the formation of the intellectual potential of society is one of the priority tasks of the State policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The state of modern education and its development trends require new system-organizing approaches to the development of the educational environment. Creation and development of high-quality and high-tech *information and educational environment* will allow the education system to make a breakthrough to an educational system that meets modern requirements.

Modernization of the technological basis of an educational institution should begin with the *formation of information culture and introduction of new information technologies (IT)* into everyday pedagogical practice.

Educational game is an active independent activity aimed at mastering specific knowledge, skills and abilities and their application in practice.

According to the definition of M.F. Stronin, “**game** is a type of activity in the conditions of the situation, aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which the self-management of behavior is formed and improved”[1.,P.15].

Game is the most active form of human activity. A flexible system of educational games allows learning with interest, and from the possibility of choosing games this interest only increases. This model of teaching, compared to the traditional one, is more promising.

In the process of teaching Russian language there are a number of interesting games. It is inappropriate to start a lesson with grammatical concepts, especially for younger students, because it leads to the fact that they quickly get bored. As a result, interest in the lesson may wane. Even the process of greeting should be started unconventionally, for example, an effective method is to start the lesson with some Russian congratulatory song (basically a motivational method for younger pupils) when the teacher enters. If the lesson continues in this way, students will not lose their attention on any task during the lesson. They even look forward to Russian language lessons. To arouse in children a steady interest in the Russian language, it is necessary to use various entertaining games, interesting riddles, poems, songs, dialog conversations. The number of children should be from 5-8 to 10-12. Within the program a break for 4-5 minutes is announced, singing and dancing are obligatory. As a result, with pleasure sung songs and poems are absorbed into children's memory, the ability to speak Russian is formed, lexically and phonetically consolidated. It is possible to specify a number of such game elements for the development of speech and assimilation of material, also manifest creative abilities of pupils, for example:

1. “**Translator**” **game**. There are several variants of this game.

1) Who quickly finds foreign words and replaces them with Russian words?

a) Many defects were found during the inspection.

b) He is writing a memoir.

c) Your arguments are convincing.

d) Everyone worked with enthusiasm.

e) We are proud of our goalkeeper

2) Who quickly finds old Slavic words and replaces them with Russian words?

a) His new cheeks are burning red.

b) The older man frowned.

c) A great city was built on the Neva River.

2. “**Line**” **game**. Arrange the synonyms in ascending order. *Ferocious, harsh, fierce, cruel, heartless, evil (enemy). Aggressive, offensive, rude, crude, crude, indecent (deed).*

A good result is given by didactic game in combination with other methods.

3. **Auction game**. In the time allotted by the teacher, pupils write as many words (pairs of words, phraseological phrases) as possible on a certain topic. Who makes more pairs of antonyms and synonyms; Who writes more words with two or three soft consonants; In which phraseologisms the word is written more head (eyes) or number seven. Who will write more nouns (adjectives, participles) that are NOT prefixes.

4. **Develop humor and imagination**. Let's dwell on one of the methods of forming schoolchildren's interest in science. It is the teacher's desire to use humor in Russian language

lessons and develop children's imagination. Almost every child is well aware of a funny comic strip. Even in a dramatic situation, according to adults, a student can see a funny detail that causes a smile or even laughter, understandable only to his peers. This is subtly felt in the book "Two-Five", V. Dragunsky's humor in "Deniska's Stories". Humor is a great helper in various situations. Let's look at some of them. The day goes on, and each Monday can be more stressful than the previous one. I will entertain the children with a humorous poem by M. Weitzman.

In conclusion, we can say that the purpose of teaching Russian as a foreign language is to develop language competences in order to ensure children's full and active participation in the life of modern society reflecting different cultures and diversity. The general goal of foreign language teaching is to form students' ability to intercultural communication, and foreign language teaching from elementary school serves as a solid basis for the formation of this ability in the future.

Literature:

1. Stronin, Mikhail Fedorovich. Teaching games at the lesson of English language : (From the experience of work). Manual for teacher// Moscow : Prosveshchenie, 1981, P.15.
2. Mirzaeva F. Of advanced pedagogical technologies in teaching professional subjects. use (methodological guide). Tashkent - 2013.
3. Sh. Akkoziev. The role of interactive methods in learning a foreign language // Three Roots. - 2017.
4. Bahromova, M. M. (2023). "AYOL" KONSEPTOSFERASIDA GENDER MUNOSABATLARINING IFODALANISHI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3 (9), 513-518.
5. Таштемирова, Замира Сатвалдиевна , & Бахрамова, М.М. (2022). ЯЗЫКОВАЯ КАРТИНА МИРА КАК ОБЪЕКТ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (2), 548-553.
6. Rustamovna, U. N., & Madaminovna, B. M. (2022). THE STUDY OF THE CONCEPT AS A UNIT OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 66-69.
7. Бахрамова, М. М. (2021). МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АППАРАТ ЭСТЕТИКИ И ФЕНОМЕН ИНФОРМАЦИИ. *Актуальные проблемы современной науки*, (4), 33-36.
8. Бахрамова, М. М., & Исакова, Д. Т. (2023, October). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРИРОДА КОНЦЕПТА И КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЕ ПРОСТРАНСТВО. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 17, pp. 22-24).
9. Бахрамова, Мунира Мадаминовна. "КОНЦЕПТ КАК СРЕДСТВО ОТРАЖЕНИЯ ГЕНДЕРНЫХ СТЕРЕОТИПОВ." (2022): 97-105.
10. Бахрамова, М. М., & Валиева, Б. (2023). ОСОБЕННОСТИ МУЖСКОГО И ЖЕНСКОГО РЕЧЕВОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ. *PEDAGOG*, 6(11), 398-403.
11. Бахрамова, М. М. ЯЗЫКОВАЯ И КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНАЯ КАРТИНА МИРА.
12. Бахрамова, М. М., & Исакова, Д. Т. (2023, October). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРИРОДА КОНЦЕПТА И КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЕ ПРОСТРАНСТВО. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 17, pp. 22-24).
13. Bahramova, M. M., & Gulfira, M. (2023). ON THE QUESTION OF THE ESSENCE AND STRUCTURE OF THE CONCEPT OF" CONCEPT". *Journal of new century innovations*, 43(2), 3-8.

14. Бахрамова, М. (2022). ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА И РАСШИРЕНИЕ ПРАВ. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (3 (81)), 39-45.
15. Бахрамова, М. М. (2022). КОНЦЕПТ КАК СРЕДСТВО ОТРАЖЕНИЯ ГЕНДЕРНЫХ СТЕРЕОТИПОВ.
16. Madaminovna, B. M. (2024). ON THE FORMATION OF SPEECH CULTURE OF THE YOUNG GENERATION. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 11(02), 247-249.